

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE FINANCING OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS THROUGH CREDIT LINES OF FOREIGN BANKS

Abstract: The purpose is to develop proposals and recommendations aimed at improving the financing of investment projects through credit lines of foreign banks.

Key words: economic , country , issues, construction, economic, bank problems, national currency, dollar, external project, investment, improve, projects, credit.

At present, credit lines of foreign banks play an important role in financing investment projects in the sectors and sectors of the economy of the republic. The practice of developed countries shows that the most optimal way to finance the country's economy is to attract foreign direct investment. Today, there are a number of problems in attracting such investments to the country, which require the attraction of government-guaranteed foreign loans and loans from foreign banks. As long as it is necessary to provide financial resources for the development of our national economy, it will be necessary to develop and improve this sector. Because the financing of investment projects in various sectors and industries of the economy, of course, will lead to faster development and stabilization of the country and increase its prospects. To prove our point, we will consider the prospects for the development of financing of investment projects in Uzbekistan through credit lines of foreign banks on the following issue:improving the investment climate. The investment climate of any country stems from its political and economic stability, and this creates an investment climate.

The development of cooperation with foreign banks will play an important role in improving the country's investment climate.

Because the strengthening of cooperation with foreign banks will increase the confidence and interest in the country. Factors that improve the investment climate include: tax on investment, expansion of customs benefits, reducing the depreciation of money, ensuring the free exchange of national currency, fully guaranteeing the withdrawal of foreign investors, increasing the level of information exchange, regional investment implementation of programs, improving the activities of infrastructure institutions, increasing the effectiveness of investment policy, etc. The inflow of foreign investment and credit lines from foreign banks into the country will improve the legal framework for investment policy in the region. Because in such relations the mutual interests of the parties collide, which leads to their mutual compromise, and such compromises are defined and regulated by legal documents at the international level. The continuation of such relations will provide an effective legal and economic basis for investment activities in the country in the short term.

Development of the national economy. Today, foreign investments and credit lines of foreign banks are attracted to the country's economy, mainly in the chemical, oil and gas, electricity, heavy and light industries, machinery,

Less materials and primary processing, processing, small business areas. This indicates that the country is gradually moving from an agrarian economy to an industrialized one. The simultaneous development of industries and sectors of special importance in the country's economy indicates the existence of strategic plans and programs in this area. Also, taking into account the fact that the country specializes in agriculture, the majority of the population lives in rural areas, the government is working to bring industry to rural areas, to develop small business in rural areas, to implement radical reforms in rural areas.

Given that the development of one sector of the economy requires the development of another sector, it can be said that the development of industry will certainly lead to the development of agriculture as well. Improving the investment climate in the country, the inflow of foreign investment and credit lines of foreign banks into the country's economy, of course, requires investment management, improvement of their valuation methods, finding and leading their most effective sources, implementation of innovations, as well as industry development. The saving infrastructure requires the well-development of institutions. Of course, the state is at the forefront of such work, and it provides the organizational and legal basis for such changes.

As a result of such changes, the activities of leasing relations, credit unions, non-bank lending institutions, insurance companies, investment companies and funds, which are an alternative method of investment, are developing and improving.

We have noted above that an cooperation with foreign banks develops, the interest and confidence of foreign partners in the country will increase. This, in turn, will allow foreign banks to develop credit lines without government guarantees, on less complicated terms, for long periods, at low interest rates, as well as in the form of syndicated lending to large investment projects in various sectors of the economy, increases. There are a number of advantages of syndicated lending, including the possibility of financing large projects, reducing the risks of local banks, direct participation of banks in direct investment, along with foreign loans to the country. It is possible to include the inflow of foreign direct investment. In addition, the inflow of such investments will lead to the financing of innovative projects in the country. This will stimulate the activities of research institutes in the country and encourage them to develop.

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